

SOCIAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE EUROPEAN RENAISSANCE

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Abstract. The article scientifically substantiates the unique characteristics of the Renaissance in European countries, its social foundations. The meaning of the word «Renaissance» is the rejection of the Middle Ages and culture, a return to the traditions of ancient (Greco-Roman) culture and art, its Renaissance. At the same time, the Renaissance is also an artistic style. Over the course of two and a half centuries, significant changes took place in Italy, and then in other countries of Europe. First of all, human thinking has changed: people began to look at the sky, earth and nature with different eyes. Unlike the previous humans, other targets emerged and were uniquely depicted in art. Because, indeed, by this time the world has changed a lot. But it was not easy to understand. In this case, it was necessary to get rid of people with a medieval mindset. For this reason, at present, people began to turn to the rich heritage of ancient culture. The article scientifically analyzed the main research and studies of the Renaissance.

Keywords: Renaissance, European countries, early stage, advanced stage, last stage, culture, art, religious and secular views.

Although the term «Renaissance» began to be used in the 19th century, these processes took place much earlier. The European Renaissance can be divided into the following stages [1, 574 p.]:

1. The first stage - XIV century.
2. Developed stage - XV century.
3. The last stage is the 16th century.

The Renaissance in Italy was mainly in the 14th century, while elsewhere in Europe spanned the 15th and 16th centuries.

The formation of the Renaissance culture took place, first of all, in connection with the deep crisis of the culture of the Middle Ages. Therefore, the main characteristic of the Renaissance is the acquisition of an anti-feudal orientation and the priority of secularism and rationalism over religion. At the same time, the crisis of religion marked a crisis in the ideological and political foundations of medieval culture.

In the mountainous regions of Northern and Central Italy, cities appeared and began to develop on these lands as early as the 10th-11th centuries, but there were no conditions for the emergence of large landownership. This led to an

increase in the status of artisans, merchants, that is, representatives of the bourgeoisie in society. Already in the 13th century, they managed to seize political power in the regions of Bologna, Siena and Florence in the fight against the feudal lords. This, in turn, led to the first signs of capitalism. A characteristic feature of the economic life of the Renaissance was the formation of bourgeois production relations.

It was also in Italy that the traditions of ancient Roman culture, especially the cities of antiquity, money and the Latin language, caused the greatest decline. Of great importance in the formation of a new culture was the preservation of historical memory of the past.

With the strengthening of the role of cities in the life of society, that is, the growth of trade relations, the growing importance of the city in social production, the development of crafts, the demand for engineers, technicians, teachers, doctors, accountants, lawyers and other educated people, i.e. engaged in mental work in cities, a special category of people appeared - the intelligentsia.

The term «Middle Ages» arose in the Renaissance and was considered a period of terrible backwardness and religious ignorance between two great cultures, Antiquity and the Renaissance [2, p.4]. The Middle Ages, in turn, is divided into early and mature periods, the first from the fall of the Roman Empire to the XII-XIII centuries, the second from the XIII-XIV centuries to the XVII century, that is, the first bourgeois revolution on the European continent. Such a periodization of the history of European countries took place in the 70-80s. In former times, this period was considered the Middle Ages, the period up to the Renaissance.

The Renaissance at its first stage did not cover all the lands of European countries, but its most developed countries. In particular, the first stage of the Renaissance dates back to ancient Italy. Renaissance ideas appeared in ancient Italy as early as the 12th century. [3, P.309]. At a mature stage of its development, it acquired a characteristic feature of the whole of Europe. At this time, crafts and trade began to develop in a number of developed European countries. People tend to move towards the city. The role of cities in society has become important. New economic relations began to be established. Serious changes have taken place in the way of life of people.

From the 12th-13th centuries, the Renaissance in European countries relied not only on religion, but also on science. The European man of the Renaissance differs from the man of antiquity and the Middle Ages in that he had the

opportunity to carry out his activities without any restrictions, to determine his way of life, to be able to manage himself [4, P.507].

The philosopher, statesman and great poet Dante Alighieri (1265-1321), who made a significant contribution to the development and development of the ideas of humanistic anthropocentrism, created a treasure of world cultural heritage in the «New Life», «Treatise on hunting through philosophy», «Party», «Monarchy». , enriched with such works as «The Divine Comedy» [4, p.57-58]. Dante's merits are especially great in familiarizing Europe with Eastern philosophical thought. In his poetry collection «New Life», dedicated to his beloved Beatrice, compiled in 1291-1292, he continues the Eastern traditions of Abu Ali ibn Sina and Ibn Rushd, glorifying true love and affection, fidelity and devotion [2, P.55-120]. In his works, Dante emphasizes that the highest human qualities are love, morality, decency, kindness, sincerity, kindness, humanity, which are considered truly human virtues. Ishk - tries to explain the process of formation and development of love, calls to respect it in every possible way.

During his exile in 1304-1308, Dante wrote one of his major scientific and philosophical works «Basm» and the artistic and philological work «People's Speech». Basm is a great encyclopedic work of medieval philosophical thought. In this work, Dante describes the awareness of the philosophical heritage as the main duty of every person. In Basm, Dante focused on the analysis of the problem of man, especially the process of forming his spiritual and moral image. According to the poet, the spiritual and moral image of each person was determined by the cultural level of society.

Dante heard Abu Ali ibn Sina's «Laws of Medicine» while lecturing at the medical faculty of the University of Bologna. Dante paid attention to astronomy, celestial bodies, Earth, Sun, Moon, planets, stars, their location and movement.

Abu Mashar (died 886) supplemented the views of the inhabitants of Iran and Mowarunnahr on astronomy in his work «Al-Muhal al-Kabir» (المحل الكبير). This work was translated into Latin in 1140 by Derman of Dalmatia.

The work of Ahmad ibn Muhammad ibn Kasira Fargani «Kitab al-harakat as-samawiyya wa jawami ilm an-nujum» (كتاب الحركة السماوية و جوامع علم النجوم). Dante was also familiar with this work. Ahmad al-Fargani scientifically substantiated the theory of the sphericity of the Earth back in the Middle Ages. The only known work on astronomy in medieval Europe is closely known as the leading representative of Dante's time.

Also, by the 12th century, interest in the science of astronomy was growing in European countries. The Jew Pedro Alfons was well acquainted with the Arabic

language, oriental sciences, especially astronomy. Alphonse served as physician to King Henry I of England in 1110. Alphonse played a large role in the spread of oriental astronomy in England and France. Under his influence, astronomy was formed and developed in England (Walcher, Adelyard of Bath, Robert Grosseteste). In particular, Grosseteste (died 1253) consistently observed the phenomena of nature and came to the conclusion that mathematical principles form the basis of existence.

In different countries, the chronological boundaries of the period have their own variations. Firstly, historical shifts in economic and socio-political life corresponded to the XIII-XIV centuries. In the next two centuries - the appearance of features characteristic of the Renaissance in Holland, France, Germany, England and other countries of Western Europe, considered the centers of the Northern Renaissance, the Renaissance process in two designated cultural centers. continued until the end of the 16th century. Specific types of Renaissance culture developed in the countries of Central Europe, including the Commonwealth and the Grand Duchy of Lithuania. Italy made a sharp turn in the economic and socio-political spheres by the Renaissance, and Renaissance culture arose in the city-states. Their prosperity was ensured by economic factors: trade and handicraft production, where a worthy place was occupied by a person who independently organized his work and free time.

The process of secularization [3, P.408] began in a number of European countries. Secularization, that is, the process of liberation from the influence of religion and the church, has reduced the influence of the Christian religion on the worldview of people. Encyclopedia, in turn, was combined with such a feature of the Renaissance culture as the unity of scientific and artistic cultures. In the Middle Ages, sciences were included in the system of «seven liberal arts». Art in the Renaissance sense of the word is not a handicraft activity, but a professional artistic method that widely used the methods of the exact sciences and claimed to have a comprehensive knowledge of the world, the unification of all forms of creativity. Much attention was paid to anatomy, which made it possible to penetrate into the internal structure of a person.

The reality of the new civilization created the conditions for an unprecedented manifestation of the creative abilities of the individual, who improved in the process of creative activity. There was a formation of a new, non-traditional type of personality, characterized by a constant desire to develop intellectual abilities and enrich the spiritual world of the individual. The new organization, working rationally on the basis of careful consideration and planning of its actions,

revised its views on the method of divine intervention in the material world, the growing trend of secularization in the culture of the Renaissance did not lead to the denial of God, but allowed the transfer of a number of demiurgic functions from the Creator to the human creator.

The development of a new type of culture was facilitated by Italian urban communes based on the principle of self-government and elections. They did not recognize the «natural law» of the lord and replaced it with a conscious socio-political agreement of equal citizens. Equality did not affect social differences, but assumed equal opportunities and not only did not prohibit, but even required individuals to develop individual initiative, independent activity, and enterprise aimed at increasing wealth.

Relations between the Renaissance and church leaders developed in different ways, cooperation was sometimes replaced by open antagonism. Developing the secular elements of culture, they did not abandon their high and spiritual categories. Rather, the search for the sublime set the tone for Renaissance writers and artists. The Renaissance was not an atheistic era, but for the first time it exposed the conflict between religion and science, and changed the very religious worldview. The most important condition for the development of the ideas of the Renaissance is the desire for scientific knowledge of nature, its ideological basis can be the doctrine of secondary truth, the «truth of faith», the source of which cannot be only religious revelation, but the creation of real knowledge based on experimental research and theoretical generalization.

The humanist of that time, Giovanni Boccaccio (1313-1375), was primarily interested in mythology in ancient culture, and in his work «Genealogy of the Pagan Gods» traced the origin and interconnection of various myths and turned his order into a pantheon of ancient gods [7, P.206-209]. Boccaccio put poetry on the same level with physics and theology in terms of a system of knowledge, which, in his opinion, also concerned higher issues. Boccaccio, who knew Greek and classical Latin, made a great contribution to the formation of the literary Italian language. As a writer, Boccaccio is known for his deeply psychological works, among which the Decameron stands out.

An important place in the fine arts of the Renaissance is occupied by the works of the Florentine painter Giotto di Bondone (1267-1337), who began to revise the concept of painting in the Middle Ages. In the works of Giotto di Bondone appeared the depth of space, shading and three-dimensional representation of figures on the plane. His paintings now not only reflect abstract ideas, but also

depict scenes close to everyday life, filled with sincere human experiences about the life of saints, the history of Christ and Mary [8, P.96].

In the era of the early Renaissance, the features of the Renaissance value system began to appear very clearly. 15th century - the time was devoted to experiments in art, more theoretical research in the field of philosophy, ethics, aesthetics, mathematics, philology, pedagogy.

The humanist movement developed strongly, as a result of which a layer of secular intelligentsia was formed in Italy. Enriching the ideas of Petrarch and Boccaccio, a new generation of humanists (Giovanni Pico della Mirandola, Lorenzo Valla, Poggio Bracciolini, Marsilio Ficino, etc.) introduced the achievements of the humanities into the intellectual environment, religion itself turned into a service to man, and also improved the worldview of the Renaissance. Musical art was further developed. Decisive changes took place in Italian art associated with the final victory of the Renaissance worldview. Differences in the economic and cultural development of individual regions of Italy led to the fact that a large number of art schools were formed in different cultural centers.

The creative activity of the Florentine masters was especially effective, they clearly demonstrated the universality of the emerging culture. Filipe Brunelleschi (1377-1446), who turned to antiquity for experience, carefully studied the preserved ancient architectural monuments, made sketches. However, from antique elements, the personality created a completely unique style.

Leon Battista Alberti (1404-1472) in breadth and diversity of knowledge can only be compared with Leonardo da Vinci. In his treatises («On Sculpture», «On Painting», «Ten Books on Architecture», etc.), Alberti posed the problem of measuring beauty and harmony based on mathematical knowledge [9, p.40-43]. A whole galaxy of talented artists appeared.

The art of Sandro Botticelli (1445-1510) combined high poetry and grace. The most famous works of the artist - «The Birth of Venus» and «Spring» [10] express the main features of his pictorial style, which are reflected in the decorativeness, lyricism, romantic sublimity of images, the ability to create a fantastic landscape, the whimsicality of female figures and giving wonderful contours. Harmoniously connecting the figures to each other, he brought an organic image to the richly decorated background of the paintings, which caused the viewers a sense of surprise. In the second half of the 15th c. in culture, the works of Italian nobles, who knew refined taste, received new privileges. In the

visual arts, the desire for decorativeness prevailed, expressed in a craving for colorful patterns, attention to detail, and bright colors.

In the first half of the 16th century, Italy played an important role in trade with the countries of the East. But because of the wars of investment in manufactory and handicraft production, trade exchange weakened, competition with Germany intensified. The fall of Byzantium had a negative impact on the Italian economy, which was based mainly on merchant capital. Thanks to the great geographical discoveries, new trade routes appeared for the coastal countries of Europe, which put an end to the monopoly of the Italians on intermediary trade with the East. In Italian agriculture, there was a trend towards agrarianization. Representatives of crisis corporations began to invest in the purchase of land, capital was invested in the agricultural sector.

During the Renaissance, mathematics and geometry were considered sciences that understood the objective nature of beauty. Renaissance artists received the most accurate information about the world through vision. Leonardo da Vinci said that only the artist's eye can see many details hidden from speculative theory.

The Renaissance developed in different countries of Europe at different levels, manifested itself in different modifications, different variants and forms. As a result of such discrepancies, European specialists have different opinions and considerations in assessing the mechanism of interaction between European culture and the philosophy of the Renaissance and the Reformation, that is, the Reformation [11, Pp.574-575].

The European philosophy of the Renaissance is fundamentally different from the mental culture of ancient times by the presence of features characteristic of medieval philosophy. One of the most important features of the Renaissance worldview, which differs from the worldview of antiquity and the Middle Ages, is that it is based on art [12, P. 68].

The changes taking place in the culture of the Netherlands concerned various forms of art, architecture and sculpture were still influenced by the Gothic tradition. The most intensive development was painting, which was characterized by a strikingly realistic depiction of male and female faces, figures, costumes of various shapes, household items, animals and plants, and depicted with careful study of the smallest details.

Early humanist ideas in Renaissance Europe were the Italian philosophers Dante Alighieri (1265-1321), Marsilius (1278-1348), Francesco Petrarca (1304-1374), Giovanni Boccaccio (1313-1375), Georgios Gemistes (1360-1425), Marsilio

Ficine (1422-1495), found expression in the work of Pico della Mirandola (1463-1495).

Also, Dutch artists became the founders of such genres as landscape, still life and everyday painting. The Eyck brothers presented the world with oil paintings, which made it possible to more freely, accurately and diversely convey the events of the surrounding world, the richness of its subjects, the personal and social characteristics of fellow citizens. The works of Jan van Eyck [13, P.64] (1385-1441) were created from the Netherlandish Renaissance artists. A series of paintings depicting people is united in the Netherlands by a common theme of glorifying God, his creations, reflections on the fate of mankind. In the transfer of perspective, the image of bodies and anatomical details, they are inferior to the works of Italian artists. However, the Dutch masters did not shy away from picturesque details, scrupulously capturing the everyday world of mountains and valleys. After the death of his brother, Jan van Eyck continued to work, creating various works. He created the image of the Madonna, painted portraits. His paintings are distinguished by accuracy and truth, the desire to show the organic unity of man and the world around him.

The portrait of the spouses, created by Javon Arnolfi (1400-1452), reached the peak of realistic skill, referring to the techniques typical for the genre of everyday life [14, B.13-18]. The portraits painted by Jan van Eyck became an element of privacy, which was a novelty in this field. The picture depicts not only a man and a woman by themselves, but also their inner unity, the warmth of the family hearth and their endless concern for each other. Even interior items here are not accidental, this is a sign of ancestral roots, expressed family fidelity, which contradicts the expanse of social life.

Later, the «aestheticization of everyday life» took shape in the era of the Northern Dutch Renaissance. Since the second half of the 15th century, the northern regions of the Netherlands, especially Holland, have become a hot center of artistic life. In the works of the artists who worked here, one can see the connection with folk beliefs, folklore, the desire to embrace not only the beautiful, elegant, high, but also the mysterious, sad, base. These features, and most importantly, symbolic art, reflected the vices of people who had drowned in a quagmire of depravity, opening a terrible kingdom of evil in the world around them.

Since the 16th century, a new direction has emerged in the art of the Netherlands, strongly departing from the medieval worldview. The mainstream of this direction was Pieter Brueghel (between 1525 and 1530-1569),

nicknamed «The Village» for his love of depicting ordinary peasants and townspeople, their holidays and everyday life against the backdrop of realistic landscapes, in the «Peasant Dance». and Hunters..

The similarities and features of the Renaissance of Central Asia and Europe are described in detail in the research works of Professor, Doctor of Philosophy G.K. Masharipova [15-24].

From the above, the following conclusion can be drawn:

1. Ренессанс даври Европа фалсафаси ўрта аср фалсафасига хос хусусиятларнинг мавжудлиги билан қадимги замон фикрлаш маданиятидан тубдан фарқ қилади. Ренессанс даври дунёқарашининг қадимги замон ва ўрта асрлар даври дунёқарашидан фарқ қиладиган энг муҳим 1. European scientists deny the influence of the East. Alexander the Great, who adopted the rites and customs of receiving eastern peoples, especially kings, did not deny this. The economic and political unity introduced by Alexander the Great and his successors did not last long, but Hellenistic culture, a mixture of cultures of different peoples, took an important place in the history of the peoples of the East and Europe.

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